

Supporting Information:

Noise and Configuration Recovery Impact on Quantum Selected Configuration Interaction

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S1 Truncated Two-Layer LUCJ Subspace Dimension

As explained in Section 2 of the main text, for each interatomic distance, an exact LUCJ simulation with 10^8 shots has been performed with ORQA, obtaining a probability distribution for the sampled bitstrings. Assuming that almost all determinants present in the truncated two-layer LUCJ ansatz are measured after performing 10^8 shots, Figure S1 shows the dimension of the subspace spanned by this ansatz for each interatomic distance along the N_2 dissociation.

Figure S1a shows the total number of different determinants sampled. Figure S1b plots the subspace dimension generated as follows: first, identify all unique α -occupations, second, construct the β -occupations by duplicating the α set, and third, create the complete set of Slater determinants by combining all possible α - β pairs.

Figure S1: (a) Total number of determinants (bitstrings) obtained for each distance in N_2 dissociation with cc-pVDZ basis and (10e, 26o). (b) Dimension of the subspace generated by the unique α -occupations obtained from the sets of bitstrings in (a).

S2 One and Two-Layer LUCJ Subspace Dimension

As mentioned in the main text, subspaces for the Hamiltonian diagonalization are constructed by sampling bitstrings from the ansatz until 4000 unique α strings are collected. Then, the set of β strings is constructed by duplicating the sampled α occupations, and the full set of Slater determinants is obtained by combining all possible α - β pairs. This yields subspaces of 1.6×10^7 configurations (red line in Figure S2b). However, as shown in Figure 1b, this is only possible when using the truncated two-layer ansatz, since sampling the non-truncated 1L and 2L does not generate enough unique α occupations to reach 4000.

When the coefficients in $e^{i\hat{J}_\mu}$ (coming from the CCSD amplitudes) are small, the addition of the rotation that “closes” the layer, i.e., $e^{-\hat{K}_\mu}$, approximately cancels the term $e^{\hat{K}_\mu}$. Therefore, the action of $e^{-\hat{K}_\mu}$ concentrates the wavefunction weight around a small set of dominant configurations. In these two cases (1L and 2L LUCJ), where the amount of determinants does not reach 4000, all the configurations available have been used, generating subspaces with the maximum size possible. The dimension of these subspaces for both ansätze and each interatomic distance considered during the N_2 dissociation is shown in Figure S2b.

Figure S2: (a) QSCI energy profiles for the N_2 dissociation obtained by sampling with cc-pVDZ basis and (10e, 26o). Violet, brown and red lines represent the exact circuit simulation carried out with ORQA for 1, 2 and truncated-2 layers respectively. Navy blue line are the data from the IBM experiment carried out in Ref. S1. (b) Subspace dimension at each point of the N_2 dissociation for 1, 2 and truncated-2 layers of LUCJ ansatz.

S3 Full space diagonalization

This section compares the energy profile for the same truncated two-layer ansatz using two different subspace sizes, the same 16 million-dimensional subspace used in the main text, and the maximum available subspace size, which corresponds to that from Figure S1b.

Figure S3: QSCI energy profiles for the N_2 dissociation obtained by sampling with cc-pVDZ basis and (10e, 26o). Gold and red lines represent the exact circuit simulation carried out with ORQA for truncated two-layer ansatz using subspaces of 1.7×10^7 and full subspace respectively. Navy blue line represents the data from the IBM experiment carried out in Ref. S1.

Figure S3 shows that, even when diagonalizing the molecular Hamiltonian within the full subspace generated by the LUCJ ansatz, the resulting energy is less accurate than that obtained from the quantum computer. This implies that hardware noise, in combination with the configuration recovery procedure, generates configurations beyond those accessible to the original ansatz, which are essential for obtaining the improved energy profile.

References

- (S1) Robledo-Moreno, J.; Motta, M.; Haas, H.; Javadi-Abhari, A.; Jurcevic, P.; Kirby, W.; Martiel, S.; Sharma, K.; Sharma, S.; Shirakawa, T.; Sitdikov, I.; Sun, R.-Y.; Sung, K. J.;

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